

**STREAMLINED GERIATRIC AND ONCOLOGICAL EVALUATION BASED ON
IC TECHNOLOGY
FOR HOLISTIC PATIENT-ORIENTED HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT
FOR OLDER MULTIMORBID PATIENTS**

HORIZON 2020 PROGRAMME – TOPIC H2020-SC1-BHC-24-2020
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**D1.1: CORE DATASETS OF HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONALS,
MULTIMORBIDITY AND INTRINSIC CAPACITY FOR GERONTE MODEL**

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the process that was used to develop the most important components of the Holis GV dashboard as well as the GerOnTe care pathway.

These are summarised as the following datasets made openly accessible via ZENODO GERONTE community at <https://zenodo.org/communities/geronte/> (See Table 1):

Table 1: Description and DOI of core datasets defined for the GERONTE intervention

GERONTE Intervention: Core Dataset	DOI (all versions)
GERONTE Description	
GERDAT002 - Composition of the health care professional consortium	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334681
GERDAT001- Core multimorbidity dataset	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334599
GERDAT003- Core intrinsic capacity dataset	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334723

In this process, we made use of various methods, including two scoping and three systematic literature reviews, patient interviews and focus groups, and finally, four survey rounds and one online meeting with an expert panel of 39 oncologic and geriatric health care professionals involved in the care for older patients with multimorbidity and cancer.

In this process, we developed five patient multimorbidity profiles based on the type of comorbidity, and the impact on decision-making as well as the subsequent care trajectory. These include:

- Profile 1 - Cardiovascular, metabolic and pulmonary disease;
- Profile 2 - Disability, dependency and caregiver burden;
- Profile 3 - Psychosocial health and cognitive impairment;
- Profile 4 - Nutritional status and digestive system disease; and
- Profile 5 - Concurrent cancer.

We established a core set of four health care professionals who should be involved in the decision-making and care trajectory for every older patient with multimorbidity and cancer within the GerOnTe care pathway (cancer specialist, advanced practice nurse, geriatrician, primary care physician); as well as an additional list of health care professionals who can be included as needed. We established standardized methods of communication and decision-making within the health care professional consortium, as well as a way of communicating with health care professionals not involved in the consortium itself.

A second step was to establish the main information components that should be included in the common medical file that is used in the GerOnTe care pathway. These include:

- 1) a large image of the patient;
- 2) personal information about the living situation and current formal and informal care;
- 3) tumour information including recommendations of the multidisciplinary tumour board;
- 4) comorbidities;
- 5) medication and substance use;
- 6) non-cancer specific prognosis;
- 7) intrinsic capacity/frailty; and
- 8) patient preferences.

For comorbidities, we developed a dataset of items that have such importance to the decision-making process that they need to be highlighted in the Holis GV dashboard. After literature review,

input was received from the expert panel. Through an iterative process, it was decided which comorbidities were relevant and how these were best captured in data to provide to the health care professional consortium. This resulted in a list of 16 relevant somatic/psychiatric comorbidities to be included in the dataset provided to the health care professional consortium. In addition to a clinical judgement of the comorbidities by a geriatrician, both for the severity of the comorbid condition as well its impact on daily functioning, we developed a list of objective measurements that could further complement the comorbidity information in the GerOnTe care pathway. A similar process was followed for data on intrinsic capacity and frailty resulting in the inclusion of 24 items across six domains.

For patient preferences, we focussed on three types of preference: outcome preferences, decision control preference, and information preference. In this process, three systematic literature reviews including one meta-analysis, were performed and two series of patient interviews. For outcome preferences, we developed a new outcome prioritization tool called ONC-OPT, which included the following outcomes: 1) extending life; 2) maintaining independence; 3) reducing pain and other symptoms; and 4) limiting negative effects of cancer treatment. For decision control preference, we found significant heterogeneity in the older patient population, meaning that it is important to solicit this preference for each patient individually. This led to the inclusion of the control preference scale in the Holis GV dashboard. For information preferences, we developed a prompt list of questions that patients can use to become aware of questions that they may want to discuss with their health care provider. We also developed a list of tips that patients can use to improve their information with their health care professionals.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

We deviated from initial grant agreement on two points:

- In the Grant agreement we had stated that we would determine which five core health care professionals should be included in the decision-making or care trajectory for all older patients with multimorbidity and cancer within the GerOnTe care pathway. Additionally, eight other members would be listed that could be included depending on the patient's needs.

We found that in our expert panel there was clear consensus on four core members, who should be involved in every patient in the GerOnTe care pathway, irrespective of the multimorbidity profile. These were cancer specialist, advance practice nurse, geriatrician and primary care physician. No consensus was reached on the fifth core member, as this was too dependent on the patient's specificities. Thus, we decided to limit the core health care professional consortium to four members, with the possibility to add others if needed.

- A second deviation from the grant agreement is that we initially stated we would determine a core dataset of four frailty components and three intrinsic capacity components. However, despite coming from a different perspective, there is significant overlap between frailty and intrinsic capacity, and we felt it was not possible to allocate specific items to either frailty or intrinsic capacity. Thus, we combined these two aspects in a single overview of items relating to frailty, intrinsic capacity or both, across the domains function/locomotor, nutrition, vitality, cognition and psychological status, geriatric syndromes and sensory impairments, social support/environment; and finally, comorbidity and medication.

Justification for delay in deliverable submission

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved on time and as scheduled in Annexe 1 (Description of the Action Part A) of the Grant Agreement N°945218.

1. Introduction

1.1. GERONTE and its objectives

GERONTE is a 5-year research and innovation project (April 2021 to Mars 2026) funded by the European Union within the framework of the H2020 Research and Innovation programme, in response to the health societal challenge topic SC1-BHC-24-2020 “Healthcare interventions for the management of the elderly multimorbid patient”. The overall aim of GERONTE is to improve quality of life - defined as well-being on three levels: global health status, physical functioning and social functioning- for older multimorbid patients, while reducing overall costs of care. To this end, GERONTE will co-design, test, and prepare for deployment an innovative cost-effective patient-centred holistic health management system, hereafter referred to as the GERONTE intervention. GERONTE intervention will rely on an ICT based application for real-time collection and integration of standardised clinical and home patient-reported data. GERONTE intervention will be demonstrated in the context of care of multimorbid patients having cancer as a dominant morbidity, and be adaptable to any other combination of morbidities.

Objectives

O1: INFORMATION gather the stakeholders and data needed for patient-centred and multi-actor complex decision-making process and management

O2: TOOLS develop ICT tools for the GERONTE intervention to be implemented

O3: METHODS develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention

O4: DEMONSTRATION demonstrate in 16 study sites from three EU countries the feasibility and effectiveness of the GERONTE intervention

O5: REPLICATION develop recommendations for the replication of GERONTE best practices in all European health systems

O6: ENGAGEMENT engage all stakeholders by co-designing the GERONTE intervention

1.2. Rationale

Deliverable D1.1 *Core dataset of health professionals, multimorbidity and intrinsic capacity for the GerOnTe model* is part of work-package 1 which supports GERONTE objective O1: INFORMATION. Optimizing the decision-making and care trajectory for older patients with multimorbidity and cancer first of all requires that all necessary information is available and that relevant stakeholders are identified and their input is included. In this deliverable we describe the process in which we developed five common patient multimorbidity profiles; established the core members of the health care professional consortium, who will take on the joint responsibility of decision-making and providing care within the GerOnTe care pathway; we also established how they should communicate with each other and with others not involved in the health care professional consortium. Additionally, we established eight essential medical information components that need to be available to all health care professionals in the GerOnTe care pathway, including information on comorbidity, frailty/intrinsic capacity components and patient preferences.

2. Methods

In the process of developing the core information components for the Holis GV dashboard as well as the core participants of the health care professional consortium, including the way they communicate, we made use of various methods. These include two scoping and three systematic literature reviews, patient interviews and focus groups, and finally, four survey rounds and one online meeting with an expert panel of oncologic and geriatric health care professionals involved in the care for older patients with multimorbidity and cancer. This section provides further details on each of these methods.

2.1. Scoping literature review on multimorbidity profiles, frailty and intrinsic capacity

2.1.1. Multimorbidity profiles

A scoping literature review was done to retrieve prior studies regarding multimorbidity profiles. An overview of the papers that were analysed can be found in Annexe 1. These formed the basis of further exploration of multimorbidity profiles with the expert panel.

2.1.2. Frailty and intrinsic capacity

A second scoping literature review was performed regarding studies on intrinsic capacity and frailty components that could be included for examination and/or intervention in the GerOnTe care pathway for older patients with cancer. An overview of papers that were analysed can be found in Annexe 2.

2.2. Expert panel input

A panel of experts was established, including medical specialists, nurses and other health care professionals with a background in geriatric medicine or involved in cancer treatment for the four cancer types included in GerOnTe (breast, prostate, lung and colorectal cancer).

In a series of monthly surveys, these experts were asked to provide their input on the relevance of various comorbidities, and intrinsic capacity/frailty items for decision-making and care for each of these cancer types and the treatment modalities that are available for them. They also provided input on the multimorbidity profiles, composition of the health care professional consortium, as well as symptom monitoring and self-management (described elsewhere). Answers from each survey round were subsequently compiled, compared with findings from the literature reviews, and taken forward to the next survey for further fine-tuning.

Each round included between 32 and 39 participants across a range of different backgrounds (doctors, nurses) and a range of specialties (medical oncology, surgery, radiotherapy, pulmonology, urology, geriatrics, general practice). Mean age was 47 years and respondents had a mean of 17 years in clinical practice. Detailed data on the composition of the expert panel can be found in Annexe 3.

At the end of four survey rounds, an online meeting was planned with a selection of the expert panel – ensuring input from each relevant background and specialty – to demonstrate how their input had

been incorporated into the GerOnTe care pathway and Holis GV dashboard. The feedback they provided was included in the next steps of the development.

2.3. Patient interviews and focus groups

2.3.1. Patient interviews

We performed two series of interviews with patients aged >70 years, diagnosed with cancer or treated for cancer during the last two years, regarding quality of life and outcome preferences. Patients were recruited during a consultation with their treating oncologist or when they were receiving treatment in the outpatient clinic. After explaining the study concept to patients, they provided written informed consent.

In the first series, the subsequent interview was done by phone at a time that suited the patient. All interviews were conducted by one interviewer. Interviews lasted between 15 and 45 minutes; patients were given as much time as needed. In these interviews, patients were asked to respond to four open ended-questions: What makes life worthwhile? What does quality of life mean to you? What could improve your quality of life? What could decrease your quality of life? If they answered with broad or vague terms, they were asked to specify as much as possible. Next, patients were asked to select the top five important determinants of quality of life. For details, see section 7.2.

In the second series of interviews, with another cohort of patients aged >70 years, diagnosed with cancer or treated for cancer during the last two years, we assessed the feasibility of using the ONC-outcome prioritization tool to assess patient preferences (for details, see section 8.2.4). These interviews were performed at the oncology out-patient clinic.

2.3.2. Focus groups

We aimed to conduct focus group meetings in which the challenges faced by older patients with cancer would be discussed as well as questions relating to the Holis GV application under development. For this purpose, we recruited non-frail or pre-frail patients aged ≥ 70 years, diagnosed with cancer (breast, lung, colorectal, prostate) in an early stage, in complete remission or in partial remission for at least 6 months; and with at least one additional comorbid condition. They were excluded if they had cognitive impairment impacting their participation, depressed mood or anxiety issues. Additionally, we set out to recruit informal caregivers for these patients.

An attempt to recruit patients and caregivers through cancer patient associations did not yield any result. Next, we provided the oncologic outpatient clinics with information flyers regarding the study, which the treating physicians could then provide to potentially suitable patients. Patients were asked to contact the research team if they were interested in participating. This process ensured their voluntary participation.

Due to COVID restrictions and the vulnerable patient group involved, we were only able to have one group meeting. To replace the other meetings that were planned, we performed one-on-one interviews in the patients' home environment as an alternative. Although this allowed for less interaction between patients and/or caregivers, it did allow for more in depth interviews.

2.4. Systematic literature reviews

In addition to the scoping literature reviews on multimorbidity profiles, frailty and intrinsic capacity, we performed three systematic literature reviews to assess patient needs and preferences:

- Patient preferences for treatment outcomes in geriatric oncology
- A meta-analysis on the role older adults with cancer favour in treatment decision-making
- Information needs of older patients newly diagnosed with cancer

Details on these systematic reviews can be found in Section 8.

3. Developing multimorbidity profiles

3.1. Defining and fine-tuning multimorbidity profiles

As part of the process of optimizing care for older patients with multimorbidity and cancer, we set out to develop multimorbidity profiles, aiming to identify clusters of comorbidities with similar care needs or similar impact on the oncologic treatment trajectory.

As a first step, a literature review was done to retrieve prior studies regarding multimorbidity profiles. An overview of the papers that were analysed can be found in Annexe 1.

In general, these studies used latent class analyses to determine types of illness that often co-occur. For the GerOnTe project, the primary focus was to develop profiles based on similar care needs or care impact, thus requiring a different approach. While the literature review did not yield any classifications that were useful for GerOnTe, it did help to develop a list of 52 potentially relevant comorbidities (Annexe 4) that were subsequently provided to the expert panel.

The experts were asked to state for each one how likely it is that the presence of this comorbidity would change the oncologic treatment decision or the care trajectory. Results can be found in Annexe 4. Items were carried forward to the next round of the survey if at least 50% of respondents scored them as being likely or very likely to change either decision-making or care trajectory or 30% or higher for both.

Combining what was found in literature with the answers regarding the relevance of each comorbid condition, we proposed five multimorbidity profiles (Annexe 5), which were subsequently presented to the expert panel. Overall, 91% of respondents agreed with the categorization of the profiles. Some respondent made suggestions for fine-tuning/clarifying the categories. Based on this input, the multimorbidity profiles that will be used for the GerOnTe project are the following:

- Profile 1- Cardiovascular, metabolic and pulmonary disease
- Profile 2- Disability, dependency and caregiver burden
- Profile 3- Psychosocial health and cognitive impairment
- Profile 4- Nutritional status and digestive system disease
- Profile 5- Concurrent cancer.

3.2. Relevance for oncologic decision-making

In the next round of the survey, the experts were asked to confirm the relevance of each multimorbidity profile for oncologic decision-making for the treatment modality that they were involved in. Scores ranged from 1 (not relevant) to 4 (very relevant).

All profiles received an overall ranking over 3 or higher, meaning it is (very) likely that the presence of a profile will influence the treatment decision. This influence is strongest for surgery and chemotherapy; for radiotherapy, only Profile 3 was likely to be of relevance (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Relevance of profile for oncologic decision-making

Next, respondents were asked why a profile would influence oncologic decision-making. These results confirm the relevance as well as distinctness of the profiles, by showing they affect decision-making in different ways. In summary, Profiles 1 and 3 were primarily considered important for determining the feasibility of surgery, systemic therapy, and to a lesser degree radiotherapy. Profile 2 and 4 were also relevant for determining feasibility of treatment but additionally, for determining the likelihood of recovery, resilience or functional/cognitive decline. Profile 5 was considered important for decision-making by affecting prognosis, treatment interactions and overall health care burden.

3.3. Relevance for care trajectory

Figure 2 shows how each multimorbidity profile was scored in terms of their relevance to the cancer care trajectory that they are involved in, on a scale of 1 (not relevant) to 4 (very relevant).

Overall, the relevance of the morbidity profiles for the care trajectory was scored lower than for oncologic decision-making, but nonetheless, respondents thought it (very) likely that the presence of Profiles 1 to 4 would influence the care trajectory (Figure 2). For Profile 5, respondents were split with equal numbers considering it relevant as not relevant.

Again, respondents were asked why a profile would influence oncologic care trajectory. Pre-treatment optimization was thought to be necessary for Profiles 1 and 4, while all profiles (with Profile 4 to a lesser degree) were considered to help in fine-tuning the support and care provided during oncologic treatment. Profiles 2 and 3 were also considered to affect treatment compliance, self-care capacity and the ability to understand treatment protocols.

Figure 2. Relevance of profile for the cancer care trajectory

Taken together, these results demonstrate the relevance of these multimorbidity profiles for decision-making and the subsequent oncologic care trajectory. However, they also demonstrate that all patients with multimorbidity and cancer are likely to require fine-tuning in support and care, and that there is no one-size-fits-all.

4. Health care professional consortium

4.1. Composition of the health care professional consortium

Another important component of the GerOnTe care pathway was to determine which health care professionals should be included in the health care professional consortium (HPC) providing care for the patient. Beforehand, we had considered the option of four core members and at least eight other participants depending on the patient's specificities or profile.

Based on clinical experience, we developed a list of 15 potential participants, including general practitioner, one or more oncology specialists (such as surgeons, medical oncologists, radiotherapists), geriatrician, oncology nurse, social worker, clinical pharmacist, physiotherapist, anaesthesiologist, home care nurse, dietician, occupational therapist, spiritual helpers/clerics,

psychologist/psychiatrist, palliative care specialist, organ-specific physician(s) such as cardiologist, pulmonologist, nephrologist, rheumatologist etc.

This list was presented to the expert panel, and they were asked to determine whether or not these participants should be involved in decision-making and/or the subsequent oncologic care trajectory; experts could specify if these participants should be involved for all patients, only in specific situations/profiles, or did not need to be involved.

For decision-making, only three (groups of) professionals were consistently chosen: oncology specialist(s) (100% of respondents), geriatrician (100% of respondents) and general practitioner (81% of respondents). Over half of respondents (56%) felt the oncology nurse should be involved in decision-making and half (44%) of respondents felt like an organ-specific physician should be involved.

For the care trajectory, four (groups of) professionals were selected: general practitioner (97% of respondents), oncology specialist(s) (100%), oncology nurse (97%), and the geriatrician. For the latter, 53% of respondents felt the geriatrician should be involved in all patients, and 44% that the geriatrician should be involved in case of specific issues or impairments.

For all remaining groups of health care professionals, it was felt like their involvement should be tailored to the specificities of the patient; no other profession was selected by more than half of respondents as relevant for all patient while their involvement in specific situations was endorsed by over 90% of respondents for nearly all professionals.

Details can be found in the dataset GERDAT002: “Composition of the health care professional consortium” published online at <https://doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.6334681>.

Based on these findings, we determined that the core of the HPC should consist of one or more oncology specialists, a geriatrician, an oncology nurse and the general practitioner. The heterogeneity of patient issues within the population of older patients with multimorbidity and cancer did not allow us to include a fifth core member as we had intended in the grant proposal. This heterogeneity, even within the multimorbidity profile groups, as well as the possibility that patients fit within more than one profile, also means that additional members should be added as needed based on the specificities of the patient and that it was not possible to point out specific additional members that should always be included in a specific profile. This does not allow for a one-size-fits-all and thus requires careful tailoring.

To facilitate this tailoring process, the possibility of adding a specific health care professional to the health care professional consortium was included in the intervention protocol detailed in Deliverable 1.3.

4.2. Communication of the health care professional consortium

4.2.1. Communication within the health care professional consortium

In order to facilitate transfer of information between the stakeholders, we worked on guidance for how relevant input for the HPC meetings is gathered, discussed and reported to ensure that communication was effective. Three of the HPC members are normally physically present in the same

location (advanced practice nurse, oncology specialist and geriatrician) and one is normally in a different physical location (general practitioner). As part of the expert panel meeting, this topic was discussed, and different options were presented. After consideration of the pros and cons, it was agreed that an asynchronous approach to communication was the most feasible. This involves the GP providing information to the other members before the HPC meeting, and the remaining three members discussing this information together (either in person or virtually). Figure 3 shows how the information is communicated into the HPC – the general practitioner is represented here by the logo “specialist advice”, which can also include other medical specialists as needed.

Figure 3: Overview of information communication to the HPC

Involving the GP in the HPC ensures that relevant background information can be used as part of the decision-making process. Our expert panel agreed that it would not be necessary to ask the GP for input on oncological decisions *per se*, but rather information that helps provide wider context about the patient and their suitability for different treatment options. This will be achieved by the APN contacting the GP in advance of the first HPC meeting. The GP will be requested to provide information with a uniform structure following these questions:

- 1- How well do you know this patient and their caregivers? Are they adequate in seeking medical advice?
- 2- How many times did you see the patient during the past year?
- 3- What is your impression of their overall fitness level? Do you think they are fit enough to undergo cancer treatment?
- 4- Can you help us to identify any issues that need support? E.g. cognition, functional, adherence, social, distress, transport, environment

4.2.2. Process of the HPC meeting for decision-making

At the HPC meeting, the advanced practice nurse, oncology specialist and geriatrician discuss patients within the Geronte pathway, using the Holis application as a structured prompting system. Holis facilitates an accessible representation of the most relevant patient information that will be used within the decision-making process. We have not been prescriptive about who leads the meeting, but generally the advanced practice nurse will present patients for discussion as they

provide regular input into Holis about the patients, including the initial set-up and completion of baseline data.

At the initial meeting (HPC decision making meeting), all the previously mentioned information topics will be reviewed and discussed, for example tumour type, co-morbidities, social and demographic factors, patient preferences and intrinsic capacity (see section 5). The Holis GV dashboard ensures this process is driven by holistic information which also permits patient involvement in their own decisions. The APN can ensure that all relevant information has been taken into account as part of the decision-making process. In order to achieve this, a structured information flow will also be a feature of the meeting. Each of the following questions will be considered:

- 1- What would the life expectancy of this patient be without cancer?
- 2- What is the life expectancy with the cancer left untreated?
- 3- What is the burden of the cancer if left untreated?
- 4- Does the cancer treatment add to the patient's life expectancy?
- 5- Does the patient have physical complaints that are likely to be resolved by the cancer treatment?
- 6- What is the burden of the cancer treatment (hospital admissions and visits, complication risk)?
- 7- What are the alternative treatment options (including best supportive care) and how would these alternative options differ with regards to expected outcomes?
- 8- What is the influence of the proposed cancer treatment on the patients' goals?
- 9- What is the cancer treatment recommendation?
- 10- What other (non-cancer) interventions are recommended?

The group of questions above was finalised at the expert panel meeting, having presented an initial list of questions obtained from a previous study by Festen et al.¹ The purpose of the original list was to provide a step-wise approach to decision making for any treatment. We modified this list to ensure it was applicable to older patients with cancer. The final list was agreed by all members of the expert panel.

As previously mentioned, patient input is a core part of the Geronte care pathway and one of the reasons why this is a novel patient-centred approach to decision making in older people with cancer. Once the initial meeting has concluded, the APN (with a physician as needed) will meet with the patient to discuss the outcome and the final treatment decision will be made together with the patient-

4.2.3.HPC meetings during treatment and follow-up

At three, six and nine months, the HPC will convene again for an evaluation meeting and take stock of the treatment plan and how it has affected the patient. The following structure will be used to discuss this in a standardised way:

¹ Festen S, Kok M, Hopstaken JS, van der Wal-Huisman H, van der Leest A, Reyners AKL, de Bock GH, de Graeff P, van Leeuwen BL. How to incorporate geriatric assessment in clinical decision-making for older patients with cancer. An implementation study. *J Geriatr Oncol.* 2019 Nov;10(6):951-959. doi: 10.1016/j.jgo.2019.04.006. Epub 2019 Apr 26.

HPC evaluation-meeting questionnaire (3, 6 and 9 months)

- 1- Is the current treatment plan still suitable? Does this treatment plan still fit the personal goals of the patient?
- 2- What issues have arisen (if any) since the last review? Are there any worrisome symptoms or signs of functional decline?
- 3- Is any extra support or intervention needed now, or likely to be needed before the next review?

The above process will continue with treatment and patient symptom reporting until the 12 month point of the timescale. Again, there will be a structured meeting to discuss progress with the following questions decided:

HPC- evaluation meeting questionnaire (12 months)

- 1- In your opinion, how successful has the patient's treatment been for meeting their priorities? (Likert scale, 1-5)
- 2- Are there any further recommendations for the patient or the treating team at this time?

During our discussions with stakeholders it was also pointed out that while the structured timeline above is appropriate for most patients, there was also a need to facilitate an additional meeting where this was felt to be necessary. Any member of the HPC can trigger this, and the following structure will be provided for discussion of the issue(s):

Additional HPC meeting – evaluation questions

1. Why is an additional HPC meeting organised?
2. What issues have arisen since the last review? Are there any worrisome symptoms or signs of functional decline?
3. What new treatment plan is considered? Does this treatment plan still fits the personal goals of the patient?
4. Is any extra support or intervention needed now, or likely to be needed before the next review?

4.2.4. Health care professional consortium reporting

Finally, the process needs to complete the information feedback loop by bringing the general practitioner into the equation. At each meeting, there is an information outflow by providing a summary of the meeting and any decisions made. This written report will be communicated to the GP by default, and to any other relevant stakeholders as needed. For example, it might be considered that a patient is having new symptoms suggestive of heart failure during the treatment programme. As a result, the HPC may decide to make a referral to a cardiologist and this information will be transmitted both to that specialist and the patient's GP.

5. Core medical components

Another task of our work package was to establish at least five medical data components that need to be made available in the common medical file (i.e. the Holis GV dashboard) for all patients.

As a first step, we asked the expert panel open-ended questions about what they felt were the biggest challenges in caring for older patients with multimorbidity and cancer (Table 1) and in what ways comorbidity/multimorbidity profiles could impact on the cancer treatment trajectory (Table 2).

Table 1. Challenges in caring for older patients with multimorbidity and cancer

Challenges	Explanation
To select the best suited treatment for the individual, balancing the uncertain benefits and risks and including patient preferences and goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of scientific evidence in this population • Best suited treatment depends on preferred outcomes • Risk of overtreatment and undertreatment • Focus still too much on the disease instead of the patient
To increase the awareness and inclusion of relevant non-tumour parameters/frailty/IC throughout the process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the decision-making process • And during follow up • Also implement non-oncologic interventions
To maintain quality of life, functioning and independence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize care (p)rehabilitation • Implement geriatric interventions
To overcome organizational challenges and improve coordination of care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of multiple HCP involved • One central healthcare professional • Organize support for the patient • Lack of time and financing
To monitor interaction and destabilization of both cancer(treatment) and multimorbidity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher risk and more impact of adverse events • Quick decline in functioning when conditions are destabilized • Monitoring cancer treatment tolerance and comorbidities frequently

Table 2. Impact of comorbidity/multimorbidity on the cancer treatment trajectory

Reasons mentioned	% of respondents
Establishing the feasibility of treatment and the risk of complications/toxicity	90%
Tailoring of support and care during treatment	83%
Estimating resilience and functional/cognitive outcomes	77%
Possibility for pre-treatment optimization	67%
Interactions between treatment for cancer and for comorbidity	63%
Predicting prognosis, competing causes of death	57%
Risk of decompensation of comorbid conditions due to cancer treatment	47%
Patient's ability to understand treatment protocols and self-care recommendations; compliance	47%
Need for post-treatment rehabilitation/additional discharge care	43%
Impact on decision-making capacity	37%
Acceptability of overall health care burden	33%

These challenges and issues include organisational, interventional, research and information aspects. For determining the medical data components that need to be included in the common medical file, the information aspects were of primary importance. Table 3 lists the eight data components that were included in the Holis GV dashboard, based on the input of the expert panel.

In the online expert panel meeting, these eight components were discussed and agreed on by the panel. In the next sections, we will discuss in more detail the core datasets that have been developed for comorbidity and intrinsic capacity/frailty, as well as the way in which patient preferences were incorporated in the Holis GV dashboard.

Table 3. Data components for the common medical file (Holis GV Dashboard)

Component	Motivation
Large image of the patient	This is to remind the health care professionals involved in decision-making and care trajectory about the person they are caring for and to maximize the focus on the person and not the disease
Personal information about the living situation and current formal and informal care	The patient has a context and this context is important for the cancer care trajectory. Being informed about the patient's personal situation and current care availability provides both insight in resources and vulnerabilities as well as opportunities for optimizing support
Tumour information including treatment recommendation of the multidisciplinary tumour board	Decision-making about cancer treatment is not possible without understanding the details of the disease. Multidisciplinary input is needed to determine treatment options, including alternatives, that can be discussed in meeting of the health care professional consortium
Comorbidities	Understanding the multimorbidity burden is essential in determining feasibility of treatment, risks of oncologic treatment-related complications or decompensation of comorbidities, as well as prognostication
Medication and substance use	Interactions between medication for multimorbidity and for cancer can be a significant complicating factor in geriatric oncology. This also applies for substance (ab)use. Furthermore, polypharmacy evaluation can assist in optimizing the patient's health status prior to initiating oncologic treatment.
Non-cancer specific prognosis	Estimating the remaining life expectancy of the patient – separate from the cancer-related prognosis – can help in choosing a suitable patient, taking into account time-to-benefit as well as time to cancer-related complications
Intrinsic capacity/frailty	This information is necessary for understanding the patient's capacity to tolerate treatment, resilience, vulnerabilities as well as for providing interventions aimed at optimizing support and health status
Patient preferences	Knowing the patient's priorities and preferences is essential for process and treatment tailoring, and for keeping the focus on the patient.

6. Comorbidity dataset

6.1. Developing dataset of comorbidities for the GerOnTe care pathway

In the Holis GV dashboard, information about comorbidities will be included in two ways. First, the dashboard provides space for listing the prior medical history in the way it is currently common practice in medical files. However, the Holis GV dashboard will also include an Avatar – an image of the patient with the opportunity to highlight specific comorbidities that have a high relevance for oncologic decision-making and/or the subsequent care trajectory. The Avatar will also include more detail about the severity and impact of the comorbid condition.

To determine which comorbidities should be highlighted in the Avatar (if present), we used the list of 52 comorbidities that was developed based on the prior literature review. We asked the expert panel to state for each one how likely it is that the presence of this comorbidity would change the oncologic treatment decision or the care trajectory. Results can be found in Annexe 4. Items were considered important enough for inclusion in the Avatar if at least 50% of respondents scored them as being likely or very likely to change either decision-making or care trajectory or 30% or higher for both. Based on these results, the following comorbidities were considered relevant for including in the Holis GV dashboard (Table 3). Items in black are included in the comorbidity overview, items in red are incorporated in the intrinsic capacity overview, and green items are included in both.

Table 3: Items from the comorbidities list selected by the expert panel for the Holis GV Dashboard

... congestive heart disease
... concurrent cancer disease
... sarcopenia, anorexia or cachexia
... severe neuropathy
... Parkinson's disease or parkinsonism
... schizophrenia or other psychotic disorders
... delirium risk or previous delirium
... pulmonary hypertension
... ischaemic heart disease
... renal disease
... COPD or other lung disease
... cerebrovascular disease, including TIA
... liver disease
... diabetes mellitus with complications
... fatigue
... morbid obesity
... cardiac arrhythmia
... heart valve disease
... an intellectual disability
... substance abuse, any kind (including smoking)
... impaired mobility, gait or balance
... anxiety, depression and other mood disorders
... dementia and other neurodegenerative disease
... malnutrition and/ or involuntary weight los
... dependence for ADLs
... dependence for instrumental ADLs
... performance status (e.g. ECOG, Karnofsky)
... dependence for instrumental ADLs
... living situation and partner status
... faecal Incontinence
... travel distance to treatment centre
... loneliness
... previous falls
... caregiver burden
... delirium risk or previous delirium

6.2. Determining relevant variables to capture comorbidity severity and impact

An important comment received from our expert panel in asserting the relevance of comorbidities was that the mere presence of the comorbidity was not sufficient. Additional information on the severity of a comorbid condition is needed to know if it impacts an oncologic decision or a treatment trajectory. Therefore, as a next step, we asked the experts to state for the sixteen somatic/psychiatric comorbidities considered important in the previous round, whether or not the presence itself is sufficient information or if they needed extra information quantifying the severity; if so, we also asked which information. Detailed responses can be found in Annexe 6.

Based on this input, it was decided that in the GerOnTe care pathway, that for each relevant comorbidity the patient has (thus included in the Avatar), the geriatrician should provide a clinical judgement regarding its severity (mild/stable, moderate or severe/unstable) and impact on daily functioning (none, limited, significant). In addition, a Core Multimorbidity Dataset of objective variables (measurements, classifications etc.) was extracted from the expert suggestions (GERDAT001 published online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334599>).

A similar process was undertaken for geriatric comorbidities and impairments; results of this are reported in Section 7 which describes frailty and intrinsic capacity.

6.3. Monitoring and self-management of comorbidities in the treatment trajectory

A final step in this process was to determine which comorbidities warrant symptom monitoring during the treatment trajectory and which lend themselves to self-management. Results of the work regarding symptom monitoring are reported in Deliverable 1.2 – DATASET OF SYMPTOMS AND PROMS FOR SPECIFIC CANCER TYPES AND GENDER. With regards to self-management, recommendations were linked to specific symptoms which could be caused by a range of comorbidities. The process of developing these symptom-specific recommendations can be found in Deliverable 1.4. – DATASET OF SELF-MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PATIENT-DRIVEN IMPROVEMENT OF INDEPENDENT LIVING. The self-management recommendations itself can be found online in the Dataset of Self-management Recommendations GERDAT004 published at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334770>.

7. Developing dataset of relevant intrinsic capacity variables

7.1. Intrinsic capacity, frailty and the geriatric assessment

In the grant proposal, we set out to determine at least four frailty components and three intrinsic capacity components to be included in the common medical file/Holis GV dashboard.

Intrinsic capacity can be defined as the composite of all the physical and mental capacities that individuals can draw on at any point in their life.¹ It is a dynamic construct: lifestyle, injuries, events at different points across the life course will have a significant impact on the intrinsic capacity

¹ Islene Araujo de Carvalho, Finbarr C Martin, Matteo Cesari, Yuka Sumi, Jotheeswaran A Thiyagarajan, John Beard. Operationalising the concept of intrinsic capacity in clinical settings .WHO Clinical Consortium on Healthy Ageing 21–22

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trajectory, as will health-related or social interventions. While there is a general tendency for intrinsic capacity to decline from mid-adulthood onward, there will be significant variation between individuals. Furthermore, intrinsic capacity may wax and wane as an individual experiences various setbacks and potential recoveries in their life course.

While intrinsic capacity focuses on the evolution of reserves over time, a frailty assessment can be seen as snapshot taken at a specific moment. Through an evaluation of geriatric domains, a patient's vulnerabilities are uncovered and used as input for modifying treatment as well as implementing interventions to optimally support the patient.

For clinical utility, intrinsic capacity has been decomposed into subdomains that can inform clinical responses, including mobility/locomotor, cognitive, sensory, psychosocial and vitality/energy domains. In geriatric oncology, the most commonly assessed geriatric domains to assess frailty include the ability to perform basic and instrumental activities of daily living (ADLs and IADLs), mobility, nutritional status, cognition, mood and social support, and geriatric syndromes, in addition to comorbidity and related medication use. Thus, there is significant overlap between these two constructs, and ultimately, we decided that it was not useful to try to separate them into items pertaining only to one or the other. Thus, instead of providing at least four frailty and three intrinsic capacity components, we decided to combine this, and provide a minimum of at least seven components across the following domains:

- Function/locomotor
- Nutrition/vitality
- Cognition and psychological status
- Geriatric syndromes and sensory impairments
- Social support/environment
- Comorbidity and medication

7.2. Initial literature review and expert panel input

As discussed in Section 6, we asked the expert panel to state for each comorbidity from a list of 52 times, including not only somatic but also functional, psychological, social and nutritional comorbidities – how likely it is that the presence of this comorbidity will change the oncologic treatment decision or the care trajectory. Again, comorbidities were carried forward if at least 50% of respondents scored them as being likely or very likely to change either decision-making or care trajectory or 30% or higher for both. Results can be found in Annexe 4. In addition to the comorbidity items identified by the expert panel, additional impairments were identified through literature review and the expert opinion of five geriatricians with expertise in geriatric oncology. These items were identified as being potentially relevant for assessing resources and predicting course of treatment or care needs (Table 4, details in Core Intrinsic Capacity Dataset, GERDAT003 published online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334723>). Aspects marked with an asterix were derived from our expert panel as being important. The other items (without an asterix) were added based literature review on intrinsic capacity and geriatric assessment in geriatric oncology (Annexe 2) and the expert opinion of five geriatricians involved in geriatric oncology.

Table 4: Intrinsic capacity data set

Items of the geriatric assessment
Frailty screening (Clinical Frailty scale)
Patient priorities (ONC-OPT)
Prognosis (Lee-index)
Somatic: fatigue *
Functional status
Dependence for ADLs *
Dependence for instrumental ADLs *
Previous falls *
Impaired mobility, gait or balance*
Performance status *
Faecal Incontinence*
Urinary incontinence
Impaired vision or hearing
Usage of walking aid
Nutritional status
Malnutrition and/ or involuntary weight loss*
Sarcopenia, anorexia or cachexia *
Cognition and psychological status
Dementia and other neurodegenerative disease*
Delirium risk or previous delirium *
Anxiety, depression and other mood disorders *
Loneliness *
Health literacy
Social support and environment
Who is the primary caregiver
Caregiver burden *
Living situation and partner status*
Transportation issues*
Use of (informal) care
Social network
Polypharmacy
Adherence problems

7.3. Assessing and grading of impairments included in the intrinsic capacity dataset

Details on how the items of the intrinsic capacity dataset may be evaluated and graded for incorporation in the GerOnTe Dashboard can be found in the Intrinsic Capacity Evaluation and Intervention protocol, GERDAT005 published online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334779>. The process of developing this protocol is described in Deliverable 1.3.

8. Developing dataset of patient preferences

8.1. Challenges faced by older patients with multimorbidity and cancer

In the patient focus groups, we asked older patients with multimorbidity and a history of cancer, as well as caregivers of these patients, what they had found the biggest challenges within their cancer treatment trajectory. These are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Challenges faced by older patients with multimorbidity in the cancer treatment trajectory

Decision-making challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to take your role as stakeholder - How to set realistic goals
Emotional challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uncertainty and worries - Psychological impact
Social challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impact on family - Impact on caregivers and other caregiver issues
Information challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dealing with all the information - Keeping track of all appointments and medical requirements - Lack of information about what can be expected during and after treatment as well as long-term effects
Multimorbidity challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of attention for health care needs and illnesses aside from the cancer trajectory - Overall health care burden - Coordination between health care providers
Medical challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to deal with symptoms and side-effects - Interaction between treatments

Again, these challenges include organisational, intervention and information aspects. For the patient preferences dataset, we decided to focus on three aspects of patient preferences: outcome preferences including goal setting, communication preferences including decision-making control, and information preferences.

8.2. Outcome preferences and goal setting

8.2.1. Systematic literature review of outcome preferences

A first step to understanding patient preferences in oncology was to perform a systematic literature review on outcome preferences in oncology. The systematic Medline and Embase search yielded 7321 hits (2042 from MEDLINE and 5279 from EMBASE). Studies were eligible if they reported some form of prioritization of outcome categories relative to each other in patients with cancer and if they

included at least three outcome categories. Subsequently, for each study, the highest or second highest outcome category was identified and presented in relation to the number of studies that included that outcome category.

In total, 4374 patients were asked for their priorities in the 28 included studies. Of this group, 79% identified quality of life as the highest or second highest priority, followed by overall survival (67%), progression- and disease- free survival (56%), absence of severe or persistent treatment side-effects (54%), and treatment response 50%. Absence of transient short-term side-effects was prioritized in only 16%.

Understanding how patients prioritize potential outcomes of oncologic treatment and the trade-offs they are willing to make is an important component of shared decision-making. Our systematic review shows that quality of life, overall survival, progression- and disease- free survival, and avoiding severe and persistent side effects of treatment are the outcomes that receive the highest priority in patients with cancer. These items were taken forward to the next steps of determining outcome preferences to include in the GerOnTe care pathway.

This systematic review was published in the *Cancers*: Seghers PAL, Wiersma A, Festen S, Stegmann ME, Soubeyran P, Rostoft S, O’Hanlon S, Portielje JEA, Hamaker ME. Patient preferences for treatment outcomes in geriatric oncology – a systematic review. *Cancers* 2022 [in print].

8.2.2. Patient interviews on quality of life and outcome preferences

The treatment of cancer can have a significant impact on quality of life in older patients and this needs to be taken into account in decision-making. However, quality of life can consist of many different components with varying importance between individuals. We set out to assess how older patients with cancer define quality of life and which components are most significant to them.

Due to COVID, larger scale focus group research was not considered possible, particularly given the fact that the target population for our research consisted of vulnerable, older patients. Instead, we performed individual interviews.

We performed a single-centre, qualitative interview study. Patients aged 70 years or older with current or recent cancer diagnosis were asked to answer open-ended questions: What makes life worthwhile? What does quality of life mean to you? What could affect your quality of life? Subsequently, they were asked to choose the five most important determinants of quality of life from a predefined list: cognition, contact with family, or with community, independence, staying in your own home, helping others, having enough energy, emotional well-being, life satisfaction, religion and leisure activities. Afterwards answers of the open-ended questions were independently categorized by two authors. The proportion of patients mentioning each category in the open-ended questions were compared to the predefined questions.

Overall, 63 patients (median age 76 years) were included. When asked “What makes life worthwhile?”, patients identified social functioning (86%) most frequently. Moreover, to define quality of life, patients most frequently mentioned categories in the domains of physical functioning (70%) and physical health (48%). Maintaining cognition was mentioned in 17% of the open-ended

questions but it was the most commonly chosen option from the list of determinants (72% of respondents).

To conclude, physical functioning, social functioning, physical health and cognition are important components in quality of life. When discussing treatment options, the impact of treatment on these aspects should be taken into consideration. Because quality of life is highly individual, simply asking patients to fill out a questionnaire is not enough to understand their definition of quality of life. It is therefore important that the healthcare provider has an actual conversation about what really matters to the patient, in which they verify what components are important and why.

This study was published in *Cancers*: Seghers PAL, Kregting JA, van Huis-Tanja LH, Soubeyran P, O'Hanlon S, Rostoft S, Hamaker ME, Portielje JEA. What defines quality of life for older patients diagnosed with cancer? A qualitative study. *Cancers* 2022 [in print]

8.2.3. Development of the ONC-OPT patient preference tool

The systematic review on outcome preferences in oncology yielded information on several methods of inquiring about patient's preferences, including discrete choice elicitation (n=15), followed by conjoint analysis (n=5), the Outcome Prioritization Tool (OPT, n=3) and various types of rating scales. For GerOnTe, we wanted an instrument that could be used in various treatment settings (curative, palliative) and that could be used in all tumour types. For this purpose, the OPT seemed the most useful. The OPT allows for an actual conversation on why a patient prioritizes certain aspects and therefore would be most suited for assessing what the various answer options mean to the individual patient.

In the original version of the OPT, a patient is asked to rate each outcome relative to other outcomes without having two values on the same level. This uses a trade-off principle: by prioritizing one outcome, patients are willing to accept the deterioration of other outcomes. The outcomes that are assigned priorities in the OPT conversation are (1) extending life, (2) maintaining independence, (3) reducing pain and (4) reducing other symptoms. During this conversation, the healthcare professional verifies if he or she understands the trade-offs correctly and invites the patient to explain why outcomes are important and how they were interpreted.

Although this tool has been used in oncology patients before, the four outcomes that are included are broad and not specific to cancer patients. Based on the information that was gathered from the systematic review and patient interviews, we decided to adapt this tool specifically for cancer patients. This was done in collaboration with the University Medical Centre Groningen (UMCG), who developed the original version of the OPT. The adapted version was given the name ONC-OPT. In this new instrument, designed specifically with GerOnTe in mind, the four outcomes for which to assign priority are: (1) extending life, (2) maintaining independence, (3) reducing pain and other symptoms, and (4) limiting negative effects of cancer treatment. We wanted to include the negative effects of cancer treatment, because it was prioritized in our systematic review after quality of life and survival as an important factor in treatment decisions.

In collaboration with UMCG, we also developed a conversation guide to assist health care professionals wanting to use the ONC-OPT tool in how to approach this. The conversation guide can be found in Annexe 7.

8.2.4. Pilot study of goal-setting using the ONC-OPT patient preference tool

In February 2022, a pilot study was launched to assess the feasibility and usability of the ONC-OPT tool in clinical practice. For this, a series of 15 minute interviews were performed with seven patients aged 70 years and older with current or recent cancer diagnosis. In addition, five health care providers using the new instrument in clinical practice received a survey to assess their experience, test the feasibility and fine-tune the conversation guide.

Patients were recruited during a consultation with their treating oncologist or advanced practice nurse or when they were receiving treatment in the outpatient clinic. All patients provided written informed consent after explaining the study concept. It was explained to patients that their answers would not influence their treatment journey and would not be given back to their treating physician. Afterwards patients were asked to fill out a form in which they rated the complexity of the method. The health care providers were asked about their experiences with the new ONC-OPT, whether all goals that patients mentioned fit in the method and whether prioritizing these goals would aid the future treatment decision. Also information on the clearness of the instructions and examples of the symptoms and negative treatment outcomes that patients wished to avoid were collected. For health care providers who had experience with the original OPT, we asked them to evaluate the difference between the new and the original tools.

Patients did not find the ONC-OPT difficult to use, but some unsure whether this tool would benefit the conversation they would have with their treating physician to choose a new treatment.

In total the ONC-OPT was tested by five different healthcare providers (all active in geriatric medicine). Of these healthcare providers four did already use the regular OPT before. All health care providers felt that they could use these new ONC-OPT to elicit patient priorities for treatment goals and most were able to fit all treatment goals mentioned by patients into one of the four categories. Sometimes, an extra explanation on the various goals was needed, particularly with regards to potential negative treatment outcomes.

In the preliminary results it thus seems that both the healthcare providers and the patients think the new ONC-OPT tool is feasible and valuable addition to the decision making process.

8.3. Systematic literature review of decision control preferences

In addition to understanding patient preferences regarding outcomes of oncologic treatment, it is important to understand patient preferences regarding decision control during the decision-making process. In the complex setting of oncologic treatment decision-making, balancing professional guidance while respecting patient involvement can be a significant challenge. We performed a systematic review and meta-analysis to assess the role adults with cancer favour in treatment decision-making (TDM), including differences across age groups and change over time.

For this, a systematic search was performed in MEDLINE and Embase, for studies on role preference of (older) adults with cancer in oncological treatment decision-making. A meta-analysis was

conducted based on Control Preference Scale (CPS) data, a questionnaire on patient role preference in TDM. The literature search identified 4,036 reports (2,071 from MEDLINE and 1,965 from EMBASE) of which 1,686 were duplicates. The remaining 2,350 records were screened based on title and abstract and a subset of 219 full text articles were further assessed for eligibility in accordance with our in- and exclusion criteria. Ultimately, 33 publications reporting CPS data were included in this meta-analysis, comprising 15,700 adults with cancer.

The results show that in current cancer care, patients' role preference has shifted towards significantly more active involvement in decision-making. No age dependent subgroup differences have been identified, as both younger and older adults with cancer favour an active treatment decision-making role. Of all adults with cancer who prefer an active decision-making involvement, two-thirds favour a collaborative role, in which they share decision responsibility with their physician.

This meta-analysis shows that the majority of adults with cancer wishes to share decision-making responsibility with their physician. However, there is heterogeneity in the individual role preferences in TDM. A minority of adults with cancer prefers to have someone else take treatment decision-making responsibility. While at the time of decision-making this may seem desirable, studies showed that a passive role in TDM, even when preferred, is associated with poorer outcomes. Patients who prefer passive TDM involvement were shown to be less content with information and communication and felt unequipped to share responsibility when it comes to making impactful treatment decisions. Thus, although it might require additional effort to elicit an active role in TDM, this effort likely yields greater patient satisfaction. A preference for a passive role in treatment decision-making should not be the resultant of a patient feeling there is a lack of time, information or space to reach their own decision. That said, the ultimate goal is not that all patients take an active decision-making role, as a passive role preference can be an active choice for the patient, and this should be respected.

This meta-analysis shows the heterogeneity within patient preferences regarding decision control. Thus, it is important to inquire about this with each individual patient. To incorporate decision control preference in the GerOnTe care pathway, the control preference scale was included in the Holis GV Decision-making dashboard, to be completed by the patient in collaboration with the advance practice nurse.

8.4. Systematic literature review of information preferences

Understanding what information patients with cancer want and need when they are newly diagnosed and faced with making oncologic treatment decision, is an important step in optimizing care. Therefore, we set out to collect all available evidence about the information that is most important to older patients with a new cancer diagnosis and whether or not these information needs are sufficiently addressed. For this, we performed a systematic literature review of Embase and Medline.

The search yielded 4137 studies (1985 from Medline, 2152 from Embase), of which 1541 were duplicates and 2569 were excluded for other reasons. Therefore, 27 studies were included in this systematic review: eighteen studies addressing the importance of information topics and thirteen

addressing the sufficiency of information provided (four addressed both). On a scale from 1-10, patients ranked information about prognosis and the chance of cure as the most important category (median ranking 10, interquartile range (IQR) 8-10), followed by information on cancer itself (median 9, IQR 5.5-9), and treatment options (median 8, IQR 8-9). Information on side-effects of treatment (median 7, IQR 6-8), and practicalities (median 6, IQR 5-7.5) were also considered important. Patients rated information about the practicalities of treatment as the most insufficiently addressed (median 9.5), followed by self-care at home (median 9), and information about prognosis and side-effects (median 8 for both).

This systematic review demonstrates that information provision about the cancer itself and about treatment options is generally satisfactory to patients, while information about prognosis, practicalities of treatment and self-care at home could be improved. However, there is significant heterogeneity among older patients regarding which information is most important to them, thus requiring an ongoing dialogue between patients and health care providers about which information is most needed at any given time.

This systematic review was published in the Journal of Geriatric Oncology: Hamaker ME, van Walree IC, Seghers PALN, van den Bos F, Soubeyran P, O'Hanlon S, Rostoft S. **Information needs of older patients newly diagnosed with cancer.** <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgo.2021.09.011>

To incorporate information preferences in the GerOnTe care pathway, we provide older patients with multimorbidity and cancer with a list of questions that may be relevant to them, and that could be used as prompts to improve conversations between patients and their health care providers. These questions are incorporated in the Holis GV patient application. In addition, tips for optimizing communications were also provided as part of the self-management library in the patient application. These communication tips and question list can be found in Annexe 8.

9. Conclusion

This deliverable describes the process in which we developed five common patient multimorbidity profiles; established the core members of the health care professional consortium, who will take on the joint responsibility of decision-making and providing care within the GerOnTe care pathway; and how they should communicate with each other and with others not involved in the health care professional consortium. Additionally, we established eight essential medical information components that need to be available to all health care professionals in the GerOnTe care pathway, including information on comorbidity, frailty/intrinsic capacity components and patient preferences. These aspects form the foundation of the Holis GV dashboard and the GerOnTe care pathway.

Annexe 1: Papers assessed in multimorbidity literature review

A. Classifications based on types of comorbidities and most common health problems in patients with cancer

- Karen Barnett, Stewart W Mercer, Michael Norbury, Graham Watt, Sally Wyke, Bruce Guthrie. Epidemiology of multimorbidity and implications for health care, research, and medical education: a cross-sectional study. *Lancet* 2012 Jul 7;380(9836):37-43.
- Helen Fowler, Aurelien Belot, Libby Ellis, Camille Maringe, Miguel Angel Luque-Fernandez, Edmund Njeru Njagi, Neal Navani, Diana Sarfati, Bernard Rachet. Comorbidity prevalence among cancer patients: a population-based cohort study of four cancers. *BMC Cancer* 2020 Jan 28;20(1):2.
- Diana Sarfati, Jason Gurney, Bee Teng Lim, Nasser Bagheri, Andrew Simpson, Jonathan Koea, Elizabeth Dennett. Identifying important comorbidity among cancer populations using administrative data: Prevalence and impact on survival. *Asia Pac J Clin Oncol* 2016 Mar;12(1):e47-56.
- Grant R Williams, Amy Mackenzie, Allison Magnuson, Rebecca Olin, Andrew Chapman, Supriya Mohile, Heather Allore, Mark R Somerfield, Valerie Targia, Martine Extermann, Harvey Jay Cohen, Arti Hurria, Holly Holmes. Comorbidity in older adults with cancer. *J Geriatr Oncol* 2016 Jul;7(4):249-57.

B. Classifications based on types of comorbidities and most common health problems in patients in general

- Mercedes Clerencia-Sierra, Amaia Calderón-Larrañaga, et al. Multimorbidity Patterns in Hospitalized Older Patients: Associations among Chronic Diseases and Geriatric Syndromes. *PLoS One*. 2015 Jul 24;10(7):e0132909.

C. Classifications based on comorbidity clusters in patients with cancer

- Erin E Hahn, Michael K Gould, Corrine E Munoz-Plaza, Janet S Lee, Carla Parry, Ernest Shen Understanding Comorbidity Profiles and Their Effect on Treatment and Survival in Patients With Colorectal Cancer. *J Natl Compr Canc Netw* 2018 Jan;16(1):23-34.
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Annexe 3: Demographic data of the expert panel (total 39 respondents)

	n=	%
Male	16	41%
Mean age	47 years	
Years in clinical practice	17.1 years	
Profession		
Nurse	4	10%
Physician	33	85%
Other (research)	3	8%
Speciality		
Surgery	8	21%
Medical oncology	12	30%
Primary care	3	8%
Geriatrics	9	23%
Other hospital-based specialist /organ specialist	4	10%
Other specialty...	9	23%
Cancer type involved with*		
Breast cancer	9	23%
Colorectal cancer	13	33%
Lung cancer	7	18%
Prostate cancer	8	21%
All cancer types	12	31%
Which treatments do you provide to patients yourself?*		
Surgery	12	31%
Radiation therapy	5	13%
Chemotherapy	14	36%
Targeted and/or immune therapy	14	36%
Hormone therapy	14	36%
None	9	23%
Other, namely	7	18%

* multiple answers per participant possible

Annexe 4: Relevance of comorbidity for cancer treatment decision-making and the care trajectory.

Percentages represent the proportion of participants stating that the comorbid condition would likely or very likely change the treatment decision or the care trajectory. Items were carried forward to the next round of the survey if they scored 50% or higher for either item or 30% or higher for both; items that fulfilled neither of these criteria are marked in grey.

	Treatment decision	Care trajectory
... dependence for ADLs	92%	81%
... dementia and other neurodegenerative disease	89%	78%
... concurrent cancer disease	84%	66%
... performance status (e.g. ECOG, Karnofsky)	82%	64%
... congestive heart disease	76%	66%
... sarcopenia, anorexia or cachexia	76%	94%
... malnutrition and/ or involuntary weight loss	73%	91%
... impaired mobility, gait or balance	71%	67%
... severe neuropathy	68%	63%
... Parkinson's disease or parkinsonism	67%	57%
... schizophrenia or other psychotic disorders	66%	64%
... dependence for instrumental ADLs	66%	78%
... delirium risk or previous delirium	63%	67%
... pulmonary hypertension	63%	51%
... ischaemic heart disease	54%	40%
... renal disease	54%	51%
... previous falls	53%	50%
... caregiver burden	53%	61%
... COPD or other lung disease	51%	60%
... cerebrovascular disease, including TIA	49%	40%
... liver disease	49%	38%
... diabetes mellitus with complications	46%	60%
... fatigue	42%	50%
... living situation and partner status	42%	64%
... faecal Incontinence	37%	33%
... morbid obesity	35%	57%
... travel distance to treatment centre	32%	53%
... cardiac arrhythmia	30%	37%
... heart valve disease	30%	31%
... anxiety, depression and other mood disorders	29%	64%
... visual impairment	29%	25%
... loneliness	29%	56%
... an intellectual disability	26%	50%
... social network	26%	44%
... severe or complicated hypertension	24%	31%
... pain syndrome	24%	49%
... anaemia	24%	40%
... inappropriate medication use	24%	49%
... substance abuse, any kind (including smoking)	24%	53%
... seizure disorder	22%	26%
... pulmonary embolism or deep venous thrombosis	22%	31%
... peripheral vascular disease or aortic aneurysm	22%	18%
... hearing impairment	21%	22%
... urine incontinence	21%	22%
... polypharmacy	19%	50%
... patients' financial worries	16%	36%
... spinal stenosis or other conditions of the spine and spinal cord	11%	14%
... osteoporosis and low energy fractures	11%	23%
... sexual dysfunction	5%	3%
... gastro-intestinal ulcer disease	3%	6%
... arthropathy or arthritis	3%	11%
... sleep disorders	3%	26%

Annexe 5: Multimorbidity profiles proposal and final categorisation after expert panel input

Part 1- initial proposed multimorbidity profiles

	1	2	3	4	5
Old	1. Cardiovascular, metabolic and pulmonary disease	Disability and dependency	Psychosocial health and cognitive impairment	Nutritional status and digestive system	Concurrent cancer treatment
NEW	1. Cardiovascular, metabolic and pulmonary disease	2. Disability, dependency and caregiver burden	3. Psychosocial health and cognitive impairment	4. Nutritional status and digestive system	5. Concurrent cancer
Including these items of round 1:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... congestive heart disease ... pulmonary hypertension ... ischaemic heart disease ... renal disease ... COPD or other lung disease ... cerebrovascular disease, including TIA ... diabetes mellitus with complications ... morbid obesity ... cardiac arrhythmia ... heart valve disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... severe neuropathy* ... Parkinson's disease or parkinsonism ... dependence for ADLs ... performance status (e.g. ECOG, Karnofsky) ... impaired mobility, gait or balance ... dependence for instrumental ADLs ... previous falls ... fatigue ... faecal Incontinence ... caregiver burden ... living situation and partner status ... travel distance to treatment centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... dementia and other neurodegenerative disease ... schizophrenia or other psychotic disorders ... delirium risk or previous delirium ... anxiety, depression and other mood disorders ... substance abuse, any kind (including smoking) ... loneliness <p>New:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... living situation and partner status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... sarcopenia, anorexia or cachexia ... malnutrition and/ or involuntary weight loss ... liver disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... concurrent cancer disease
Other comorbidities		Rheumatologic diseases (including PMR and auto-immune disease)**		Colitis (auto-immune disease)**	

Part 2- Final multimorbidity profiles after expert panel input

	1	2	3	4	5
Name	Cardiovascular, metabolic and pulmonary disease	Disability and dependency	Psychosocial health and cognitive impairment	Nutritional status and digestive system	Concurrent cancer treatment
Included items from round 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... congestive heart disease ... pulmonary hypertension ... ischaemic heart disease ... renal disease ... COPD or other lung disease ... cerebrovascular disease, including TIA ... diabetes mellitus with complications ... morbid obesity ... cardiac arrhythmia ... heart valve disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... severe neuropathy ... Parkinson's disease or parkinsonism ... dependence for ADLs ... performance status (e.g. ECOG, Karnofsky) ... impaired mobility, gait or balance ... dependence for instrumental ADLs ... previous falls ... fatigue ... faecal Incontinence ... caregiver burden ... living situation and partner status ... travel distance to treatment centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... dementia and other neurodegenerative disease ... schizophrenia or other psychotic disorders ... delirium risk or previous delirium ... anxiety, depression and other mood disorders ... substance abuse, any kind (including smoking) ... loneliness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... sarcopenia, anorexia or cachexia ... malnutrition and/ or involuntary weight loss ... liver disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... concurrent cancer disease
New		Rheumatologic disease			

Annexe 6: – Variables suggested to describe severity of comorbidity

Comorbidities	% stating presence alone is sufficient	Examples of suggested variables for capturing severity			
Anxiety, depression and other mood disorders	20%	medication	current or history	compliance	current symptoms
Cardiac arrhythmia	41%	type of arrhythmia	treatment required		
Cerebrovascular disease	27%	frequency of CVA's	cognitive function	affecting ADL- iADL	
Concurrent cancer disease	10%	(previous) treatment	stage of disease	prognosis	
Congestive heart disease	24%	LVEF	NYHA (symptoms)	Recent hospitalisation	
COPD or other lung disease	17%	GOLD	symptoms/ impact on ADL		
Diabetes mellitus with complication	60%	many different answers	hba1c	severity of symptoms- impact on ADL	
Heart valve disease	24%	severity (unspecified)	impact on ADL	LVEF	
Ischaemic heart disease	20%	similar as congestive heart disease	LVEF	past treatment	symptomatic/st able
Liver disease	17%	child pugh	billirubin and "liver function tests"	cause of liver disease	
Morbid obesity	83%	BMI			
Parkinson's disease or parkinsonism	34%	cognitive function	severity of symptoms	functional impairment	prognosis
Pulmonary hypertension	49%	different answers	symptoms/NYH A	impact on ADL	
Renal disease	17%	GFR			
Schizophrenia or other psychotic disorders	33%	stable or not	severity of symptoms	adherence	interference with treatment
Severe neuropathy	65%	functional impairment- impact on ADL			
Substance abuse, any kind (including smoking)	47%	quantification	what abuse		

Annexe 7: Conversation guide for the ONC-OPT tool

Background

The Outcome Prioritization Tool (OPT) is a conversation guide/method that can assist you when discussing preferences for treatment goals and outcomes with patients. This information can be used to provide tailored recommendations for oncologic treatment choices. The ONC-OPT is an adaptation of the OPT tool, tailored to the oncologic setting.

Using the ONC-OPT, patients are asked to rank and prioritize treatment goals from most to least important. Included goals are extending life, maintaining independence, reducing or eliminating pain or other symptoms, and preventing negative treatment effects. Patients are asked to rate each goal with a number between 0 and 100, representing the importance of the goal. The exact number is not important, what matters is the difference in rating between the various goals.

Being asked to prioritize will help the patient understand that there are trade-offs to be made. Prioritizing one goal could be at the cost of another. The health care provider will gain more insight into what matters most to the patient, and which concessions they are or are not willing to make, as well as their reasons. For health care providers, it is important to understand how the patient interprets each goal, for example, what maintaining independence means to them in their particular circumstances. The ONC-OPT is a conversation guide to discuss what matters to patients; it is not a decision aid. The results of the ONC-OPT conversation will be taken into consideration in the shared-decision making discussion the oncologic specialist will have with the patient (and caregivers).

Instructions for patients

As a nurse/physician, it is important to me to understand what matters to you. This can help in choosing the most appropriate treatment for you.. In the conversation we are going to have now, we will not be choosing a specific treatment option. We will try to clarify what is most important to you in your life. A treatment option can have positive or negative effects. This could be a reason you don't want to choose that treatment. For example, a treatment that may help you live longer, could be so tough that it means your physical condition declines so that you need more help from others to cope.

Now I am going to go through the different goals with you.

1. Extending life: Aiming to live as long as possible
2. Maintaining independence: Aiming to be as independent as possible in your daily activities
3. Reducing or eliminating pain and other symptoms.

Are there any specific symptoms you would like to reduce or avoid?

(If the patient doesn't name any symptoms, you can give examples: pain, dizziness, fatigue, shortness of breath)

4. Preventing negative effects of treatment: Aiming for a treatment that has the least chance of having negative effects.

Are there specific side-effects or other negative effects of treatment that you would like to avoid if at all possible?

(If the patient doesn't mention any examples, you could mention: loss of feeling in your fingers, incontinence, increased risk of infection, cognitive decline, hair loss.)

Looking at these goals, which is most important to you?

Where would you rate this goal on a scale of 0 to 100? The higher you place the goal, the more important it is to you. The exact number is not important, what matters is which goals you prioritize and how close together or far apart the different goals are. As you are thinking about this, I would like to ask you not to place two goals on the same level, but to really make a choice about which is the most important. There is no wrong or right answer, it is about what matters most to you.

So for you ... is the most important. What does that mean to you? What are you trying to avoid?

Sometimes, a treatment could benefit one goal but could have a negative effect on another goal. That is why it's important for you to realize that if you prioritize this may mean you need to accept a less positive effect on another goal. For example, if you give highest priority to maintaining independence, this means you should also be willing to possibly live less long in order to maintain your independence as much as possible.

Let's look at the second highest priority. What is the next one for you, after ...

(Continue like this until all goals have been given a ranking)

Annexe 8: Communication tips for patients and questions prompt list

Communication tips to prepare for your next consultation with your health care provider

To make the most of your health care providers, it is a good idea to prepare for your next consultation.

- Take some time to think about what you want to know about your disease, symptoms and possible treatments. It will help both you and your health care providers if you are clear about what you want to know (and what you don't want to know).
- Write down any questions you may have beforehand. This list may give you some ideas of questions you might want to ask ([LINK TO QUESTIONS LIST](#)). Think about which questions have the highest priority for you, so you can ask those questions first.
- Bring someone with you to the consultation. If you are afraid to ask a question, your family member, friend or caregiver can do this for you. Two people will remember more than one person, and being in the consultation together will make it easier to discuss what was said. You can consider recording the conversation with your health care provider, but be sure to ask permission for this first.
- Ask your health care provider how much time they have; it may be necessary to plan a second consultation.
- Always bring a medication list to the consultation
- If you have trouble understanding what is being said or if you are feeling unsure about something, ask questions. Also ask your health care provider to explain medical terms that you don't understand. If they speak too quickly, ask them to slow down.
- Repeat what was said in your own words, so you can check if you have understood and your health care providers knows if everything is clear
- It may be a good idea to take some notes, so that you can reread what was said later on.
- If you need to make a difficult decision, ask for time to consider your options. Also ask how much time you can take to think about it.
- Ask if there is any written information or useful websites you could consult to get more information on paper
- Ask who you should contact if you have any further questions.

Questions list

Cancer itself	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is my diagnosis? • How did I get this?
Prognosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What can you tell me about my prognosis? • Will treatment make me feel better? • Will treatment make me live longer? • What can I expect for the future? Will I get other complaints? • How will I know if the treatment was successful? • How will I know if the cancer came back? • What will happen to me if the cancer cannot be cured? • With whom can I discuss my advance directives? • What happens if I find the treatment too burdensome?
Decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where can I find more information? • Is there a patient support group I can contact? • Should I get a second opinion? • Who can help me if I am struggling to make a treatment decision?

Treatment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did you inform my primary care physician about my diagnosis? • What can you or another health care provider do about this illness? • Do I have a choice regarding treatment? • Why is this treatment the best option? • What is the goal of this treatment? • What are the expected benefits of this treatment? • What are the risks of this treatment? • What happens if I do not get treatment? • What are the advantages and risks of postponing treatment? • Are there any other treatment alternatives and what are the risks and benefits? • What happens if I change my mind and want to stop the treatment? • Are there other treatment options available if the first treatment does not work or the cancer comes back?
Practicalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will the treatment or test be painful? • When will I get the results of the test? • May I take someone to accompany me to the test/treatment? • How long will the treatment take? • Where will the treatment take place? • What does my follow-up look like? Will I keep getting check-ups? • Are there any specific signs or symptoms I need to watch for during follow-up? • Will you remain my health care provider? • Which health care providers are available for my living situation? • Which hygiene measure do I need to take? • Where can my partner/family go for more information? • Who can I contact if I have problems or questions?
Side-effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What side-effects should I expect from this treatment? • When will side-effects occur and how long will these side-effects last? • Are there any side-effects that I should pay particular attention to or report during treatment? • Who can I contact if I have side-effects? • I am suffering from a specific complaint, is there anything you or I can do to alleviate my complaints? • Are there any preventive measures I can take?
Self-care at home	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the best way to care for myself before or during treatment? • What can I do to recover more quickly?
Functioning and quality of life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How long will it take me to recover from this test/treatment? • How will this treatment affect my life now and in the future? • Will I be able to still do my normal daily activities after the treatment, both in the short and the long term? • How will this treatment affect my quality of life? • Is there anything you or I can do to improve my functioning or quality of life?
Dealing with after-effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where can I get coping support if I am struggling with emotional after-effects? • What can be done to deal with physical after-effects? What can I do myself? Can I get professional help?

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